

Biodiversity Survey of the Cape (BioSCape) Earth Science Applications Report

2024 Annual Report (Year 4)

PI's: Adam M. Wilson & Erin Hestir; South African PI: Jasper Slingsby;
Science Team Manager: Anabelle Cardoso; Applications Coordinator: Cherié Forbes
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Summary

BioSCape, or the Biodiversity Survey of the Cape, is NASA's first biodiversity-focused airborne and field campaign that took place in South Africa in late 2023. BioSCape aims to better understand the structure, function, and composition of ecosystems, and to learn about how and why they are changing in time and space. In doing so, BioSCape brings us closer to being able to track progress towards the goals and targets laid out in the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework ("The Biodiversity Plan"). The inclusion of an Earth Science Applications component in an airborne and field campaign is unusual. BioSCape thus represents an exciting opportunity to learn how these campaigns can have impact and be leveraged to help NASA meet its Earth Science to Action Objectives while also contributing to improved monitoring and reporting of biodiversity at various scales and across various realms to The Biodiversity Plan. This could be especially valuable where the campaign is a pathfinder or highly aligned with upcoming orbital missions, as is the case with BioSCape. BioSCape has taken advantage of these opportunities and achieved several important impacts to date. These include:

- Increasing awareness of NASA Earth Data and its utility for South African applications.
- Contributing to building and maintaining the BioSCape Community of Practice.
- Capacity building and Open Science to increase the future benefit of NASA's Earth Data.
- Science communication to promote positive perception of NASA's Earth Data.

BioSCape also identified several important potential end-user needs for NASA's Earth Data. These include:

- NASA Earth Data for the South African National Biodiversity Assessment and Associated National Biodiversity data products. These products feed directly into South Africa's reporting to the Convention on Biological Diversity.
- NASA Earth Data for water quality measurement and monitoring.
- NASA Earth Data for management of invasive alien plants.

In the coming year, BioSCape plans to continue its positive track record by:

- Continuing to develop and document the impact of BioSCape in South Africa and globally.
- Continuing to document the realized and potential impact of other NASA Earth data and the way that BioSCape data products support this impact.
- Additionally, we are actively looking for additional funding to support a second Earth Science Applications Workshop in 2025.

This report was open to comment from the BioSCape Science Team, and all community feedback was incorporated before submission to NASA HQ. An accompanying document, the 'BioSCape Annual Report', details the general science and operations updates from the project.

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List of Common Acronyms

CapeNature	CapeNature is a public entity who is mandated by the government to be responsible for biodiversity conservation across the Western Cape province, including the management of land and marine protected areas.
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity.
CFRP	Cape Floristic Region Partnership. A regional network that supports diverse stakeholders to better conserve the unique biodiversity of the Greater Cape Floristic Region.
CSIR	Council for Scientific and Industrial Research. A public entity, one of South Africa’s research councils mandated to conduct research.
DEA&DP	The provincial Department of Environmental Affairs and Development Planning.
DFFE	South Africa’s National Department of Forestry, Fisheries, and Environment.
DWS	South Africa’s National Department of Water and Sanitation.
NBA	National Biodiversity Assessment of South Africa. The official national evaluation of South African biodiversity, mandated to be produced by SANBI.
NEMBA	South African National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Act. This act dictates the laws for the management and conservation of South Africa’s biodiversity, including the protection of species and ecosystems.
NIAPS	The South African National Invasive Alien Plant Surveys.
NRF	South African National Research Foundation, equivalent of the United State’s National Science Foundation.
OCIMS	National Oceans and Coastal Information Management System. A suite of government-run decision support tools.
SAEON	The South African Environmental Observation Network. A national government research facility charged with conducting and facilitating long-term ecological and environmental observation and research (similar to NEON and LTER in the USA).
SANBI	South African National Biodiversity Institute. A public entity who is mandated to monitor and report on the state of biodiversity in South Africa.
SANSA	South African National Space Agency, equivalent of the United States’ NASA.
SOBR	State of Biodiversity Report. The provincial report on biodiversity, mandated to be produced by CapeNature.
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.
WCG	The Western Cape Provincial Government.

Earth Science to Action and Earth Science Applications

BioSCape took place in the Greater Cape Floristic Region of South Africa and aims to better understand biodiversity through three main research themes: i) shifting community composition, ii) ecosystem disturbance, resilience, and recovery, and iii) ecosystem function and nature's contributions to people. The airborne data collection component of BioSCape involved four airborne NASA instruments and two South African instruments aboard two of NASA's aircraft and one South African aircraft. Airborne observations were accompanied by a diversity of field measurements, collected by 19 Principal Investigator (PI) led research teams across terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. Orbital acquisitions from EMIT, ECOSTRESS, GEDI, Landsat, MODIS, and the Sentinel sensors complemented the airborne and field data sets. BioSCape is NASA's first biodiversity-focused field campaign that started scoping in 2015, collected the majority of its data in the last quarter of 2023, and hopes to advance the impact of NASA Earth science to benefit all humankind in the coming years through [Earth Science Applications](#) and in line with NASA's [Earth Science to Action strategy](#) (Figure 1) as outlined below.

BioSCape's contributions towards Earth Science to Action Objective 1: *Holistically Observe, Monitor, and Understand the Earth System* are outlined in the accompanying Annual Project Report, while BioSCape's contributions to Objective 2: *Deliver Trusted Information to Drive Earth Resilience Activities* are outlined in this report. Within Objective 2, BioSCape's Earth Science Applications activities focused on progressing the following Earth Science to Action Key Results:

- Key Result 2.2: Co-designed solutions and tools to support users
- Key Result 2.3: Science-based information we can trust and act on
- Key Result 2.4: Promotion of Earth information as a national asset

Figure 1: NASA's Earth Science to Action Strategy (from NASA).

To achieve these key results, NASA's Applied Science program, under which BioSCape Earth Science Applications activities fall, helps end users use NASA data to inform decision-making and address real-world issues. As such, Earth Science Applications represent the link from basic research to real-world uses of that knowledge. Monitoring and evaluating Earth Science Applications involves analyzing the changes that result from a project and is done by evaluating Impact.

Impact is the social and economic benefits stemming from improved decisions and actions as a result of end users engaging with NASA Earth Data. Impact is progressive, and includes many levels of end user engagement with NASA Earth Data, for example:

- Awareness of the data
- Realization that the data can inform their work
- Willingness to try using the data
- Confidence in searching for better data to answer their questions
- Integration of the data in their decision-making processes
- User adoption, adaptation, and maintenance of the data and related products
- Future development of the data products

Impact can be measured by assessing Uptake, which is the sustained use and user management of applications, Reach, which is the number and breadth of people and organizations engaged in applied projects and activities, and Value, which is the benefits accrued through program activities. Uptake, Reach, and Value can be measured in the following ways:

- Knowledge Gain: Improvement in understanding or ability to use NASA Earth Data
- Use: Amount of NASA Earth Data use by end users
- Change in Behaviour: Decisions made by end user with NASA Earth Data
- Awareness and Perception: NASA Earth Data awareness and perceived value
- Benefit: Benefit to end users resulting from NASA Earth Data use
- Sustainability: Long-term continued use of NASA Earth Data

In this report, we will present BioSCape's impact to date, opportunities for potential future impact, and highlight various application-relevant outputs and outcomes.

The primary goal of airborne and field campaigns is not to maximize Earth Science Applications impact, but instead to calibrate and validate satellite instruments and support sensor and algorithm development. However, airborne and field campaigns are a crucial component of NASA's integrated approach to Earth system science (**Figure 2**), and represent a significant financial investment. As such, leveraging airborne and field campaigns to increase Earth Science Application impact is desirable.

Being primarily once-off and geographically-limited (cf. orbital missions), BioSCape has limited opportunity for impact via sustained use. However, campaigns that fly multiple payloads (i.e. more than one instrument) on one aircraft, as BioSCape did, are efficient and optimize, together with field validation, understanding ecosystem dependencies and interactions and meet the priorities outlined in the Decadal Survey for Earth Science and Applications from Space (Committee on the Decadal Survey for Earth Science and Applications from Space et al., 2018). BioSCape's contemporaneous acquisitions by four NASA instruments, and especially coincident measurements by AVIRIS-NG and PRISM from a single airborne platform, make this dataset exceptionally well suited to advance the Earth Science Applications of upcoming orbital missions like SBG as well as current NASA Earth data missions like EMIT, PACE, ECOSTRESS, and GEDI. This report outlines multiple ways in which BioSCape is doing this, all of which aid in identifying and building early adopter communities.

Being one of the first airborne and field campaigns to have an Earth Science Applications component, BioSCape represents an exciting opportunity to learn how field campaigns can have Earth Science Applications and be leveraged to help NASA meet its Earth Science to Action Objectives.

Figure 2: How airborne science integrates within Earth system science research. Earth system science research involves spaceborne, airborne, and field observations as well as modeling and laboratory studies (from (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2021).

The Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and South Africa’s National Environmental Management Biodiversity Act

South Africa is a signatory of the Convention of Biological Diversity (CBD) and mandated to report on progress towards the [Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework](#) (‘The Biodiversity Plan’). Reporting on biodiversity in South Africa is done at the national level, and thus it’s unlikely that BioSCape data products will feed directly into the headline indicators. However, through our collaboration with the South African National Biodiversity Institute ([SANBI](#)), **BioSCape is anticipated to impact several of The Biodiversity Plan’s Goals and Targets** as outlined below and is likely to contribute valuable case studies that may inform national-level monitoring and action in future.

<p>BioSCape Impact</p>	
<p><u>Goal A:</u> Protect and Restore</p>	<p>BioSCape will contribute towards mapping ecosystem extent and integrity/condition, for example, mapping different functional communities and alien plant invasions or selected taxa. BioSCape will also contribute to population, distribution and data on threats that underpin species and ecosystem threat assessments.</p>

<p><u>Goal D:</u> Invest and Collaborate</p>	<p>Through significant investment by the United States and South African governments, BioSCape is building technical capacity in both countries. The project is an example of positive international cooperation working towards equitably Open Data practices.</p>
<p><u>Target 1</u> Plan and Manage all Areas To Reduce Biodiversity Loss</p>	<p>Develop and test new technologies and methods to produce data products relevant to biodiversity-inclusive spatial planning and effective management processes.</p>
<p><u>Target 2</u> Restore 30% of all Degraded Ecosystems</p>	<p>By helping to identify degraded ecosystems and indicators of recovery, BioSCape can inform restoration planning and monitoring efforts.</p>
<p><u>Target 3</u> Conserve 30% of Land, Waters and Seas</p>	<p>By helping identify biodiversity hotspots and key novel habitats and by assessing the threats to and condition of ecosystems, BioSCape will help inform conservation planning and management. Improved mapping of ecosystem extent contributes to improved planning and reporting.</p>
<p><u>Target 4</u> Halt Species Extinction, Protect Genetic Diversity, and Manage Human-Wildlife Conflicts</p>	<p>BioSCape is contributing towards conservation of threatened species by helping to build a better understanding of distribution and abundance trends, for example through audio monitoring of birds and a better understanding of the relationship between species and ecosystems.</p>
<p><u>Target 6</u> Reduce the Introduction of Invasive Alien Species by 50% and Minimize Their Impact</p>	<p>BioSCape is helping create maps of invasive alien species and increasing our understanding of how they affect ecosystem function. This can assist efforts to eliminate, minimize, reduce and mitigate their impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem services.</p>
<p><u>Target 7</u> Reduce Pollution to Levels That Are Not Harmful to Biodiversity</p>	<p>BioSCape is helping develop better Harmful Algal Bloom detection algorithms that will benefit monitoring of coastal and inland water eutrophication, aiding pollution management and aquaculture, mariculture, and fisheries industries.</p>
<p><u>Target 11</u> Restore, Maintain and Enhance Nature's Contributions to People</p>	<p>BioSCape will contribute towards better management of terrestrial invasive alien species. This is an essential part of maintaining and improving freshwater supply, reducing fire hazards, and maintaining biodiversity and the aesthetic of landscapes.</p>
<p><u>Target 14</u> Integrate Biodiversity in decision making at Every Level</p>	<p>BioSCape's research is relevant to decision-makers in South Africa, and we hope to bring the BioSCape data products to these decision-makers as they are produced.</p>
<p><u>Target 20</u> Strengthen Capacity-Building, Technology Transfer, and Scientific and Technical Cooperation for Biodiversity</p>	<p>BioSCape is engaged in capacity-building and scientific cooperation in a developing country and strongly focuses on co-developing joint scientific research, skills, and technology transfer.</p>
<p><u>Target 21</u> Ensure That Knowledge Is Available and Accessible To Guide Biodiversity Action</p>	<p>BioSCape is making a concerted effort to ensure that all campaign data follows Open Science principles and is equitable - for example, the BioSCape Cloud Environment reduces barriers to access for South African users.</p>

In addition to being a signatory on the CBD, South Africa also has national and provincial legislation mandating the conservation of biodiversity (**Figure 3**). The largest and most impactful of these is the National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Act ([NEMBA](#)). NEMBA dictates the laws for the management and conservation of South Africa's biodiversity, including the protection of species and ecosystems. NEMBA also established SANBI, which is mandated to monitor and report on the state of biodiversity in South Africa. SANBI's primary reporting mechanism is the publication of the National Biodiversity Assessment ([NBA](#)) every seven years, with the next NBA scheduled for release in 2025. The NBA is based on remote sensing and field data and serves several important purposes (Skowno et al., 2019):

- It informs policies and strategies in the biodiversity sector (including where and how to expand protected areas) and other key sectors responsible for natural resources utilization and/or protection, such as water, agriculture, fisheries, and mining.
- It provides information to help prioritize the often-limited resources for managing and conserving biodiversity; including datasets that feed into site and regional-level planning and assessment (e.g., Strategic Environmental Assessments and Environmental Impact Assessments) and provincial and municipal Bioregional Plans and Marine Spatial Plans (i.e., systematic biodiversity planning).
- It creates a key reference and educational work for use by scientists, students, consultants, decision-makers, and funders.
- It serves as an effective national-level platform for encouraging and facilitating collaboration, information sharing, and capacity building in the biodiversity sector in South Africa.
- It provides for a range of national and international level monitoring, reporting, and assessment processes such as state of environment reporting and reporting on commitments to international conventions (e.g., linked to the United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity, the Sustainable Development Goals and the Intergovernmental science-policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services).

The NBA is done at a national level, but provincial assessments are also undertaken semi-regularly. Given that the field campaign acquired data over ~35% of the extent of the Western Cape Province, we anticipate that **BioSCape will likely impact the 2025 NBA by contributing case studies highlighting the potential for biodiversity monitoring with imaging spectroscopy and Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR). This will pave the way for future impact on biodiversity conservation in South Africa when these kinds of data (satellite and field) are available for the whole country and can contribute to the national headline indicators used in the NBA, such as ecosystem and species threat assessments.**

BioSCape's focus on the Western Cape province also means it will likely inform the provincial-level State of Biodiversity Report ([SOBR](#)), which is legislated by the Western Cape Biodiversity Act. This act enforces reporting on the state of biodiversity and contributes to larger conservation strategies. The SOBR is prepared by [CapeNature](#) every five years (last prepared in 2023). CapeNature is the entity responsible for biodiversity conservation across the province, which includes managing land and marine protected areas, and the SOBR is a key component of their Strategic Adaptive Management strategy. As such, **BioSCape has potential to improve the SOBR and impact conservation decision making by helping authorities respond to change and improve biodiversity management.** BioSCape is mentioned in this context in the 2023 SOBR, despite the report being prepared before the field campaign.

In addition to provision of airborne- and field-derived data products, **BioSCape also has potential to impact both the NBA and the SOBR in the future through increased**

awareness of NASA Earth Data, helping end users realize that these data can inform their work, and activities that increase end users willingness to try using these data. This is as a result of BioSCape’s suite of awareness-raising and capacity-building activities, that not only cover the campaign’s airborne datasets but explicitly tie these to orbital assets including EMIT, ECOSTRESS, GEDI, PACE, Landsat, MODIS, the Sentinel sensors and SBG (detailed later in this report).

South Africa has a reputation for having “set the standard” for using scientific information in conservation planning and implementation (Balmford, 2003; Buschke et al., 2019). Strong personal and institutional relationships among scientific research institutes, environmental management authorities, and conservation managers have led to rapid dissemination and uptake of novel science relevant to decision-making, and the local scientific community is deeply engaged with research that speaks to the information needs of stakeholders (Gelderblom & Wood, 2018). There is, therefore, good reason to believe that BioSCape’s data products will be taken up and effectively implemented here and that this will help inform the management of similar ecosystems worldwide.

Based on work by Andrew Skowno (SANBI)

Figure 3: Schematic of organizations affiliated with BioSCAPE and discussed in this report and their role in biodiversity decision making in South Africa. The color of the boxes corresponds to which decisions each organization plays a role: blue represents biodiversity data collection, red indicates reporting and policy development, green represents land management, and yellow represents the definition of research questions.

Increasing Awareness of NASA Earth Data and its Utility for South African Applications

To increase the likelihood of sustained use of BioSCAPE and NASA Earth Data, BioSCAPE engages in multiple awareness-raising activities. **These activities impact South African end users by making them more aware of the data, realizing that it can inform their work, and**

being more willing to try and use the data. These activities and their key outcomes are outlined below.

Engagement with South African Government Institutions

BioSCape has engaged extensively with the South African provincial Western Cape Provincial Government (WCG) and in particular their Department of Environmental Affairs and Development Planning (DEA&DP). BioSCape meets with this government department every 2-4 weeks. Additionally, BioSCape gave an invited seminar at the Department's Ecological Infrastructure Investment Framework workshop in August 2023. As a result of sustained engagement with the provincial DEA&DP, BioSCape has achieved the following **outcomes**:

- Official endorsement of BioSCape by the Premier (comparable to the Governor of a state in the United States), the Minister of DEA&DP, and the Head of the Department of Agriculture. These letters i) set aside government employee time to engage with BioSCape and ii) expressed enthusiasm for the potential of BioSCape and related spaceborne remote sensing data for biodiversity conservation, agriculture, water and other applications in the province.
- A better understanding of the research to policy to practice pipeline and its common roadblocks.

BioSCape has worked closely with and found strong support from the South African Environmental Observation Network ([SAEON](#)) since the pre-proposal phase in 2015. SAEON is a national government research facility charged with conducting and facilitating long-term ecological and environmental observation and research (similar to [NEON and LTER](#) in the USA). SAEON is based within the National Research Foundation ([NRF](#)) (South Africa's equivalent of the US's National Science Foundation) and reports to the South African National Department of Science and Innovation (DSI). The outcomes of this collaboration include:

- SAEON has supported BioSCape at various levels from institutional support within the South African political sphere to the inclusion of SAEON aerial, terrestrial, and marine research platforms in data collection as part of the campaign.
- Many SAEON staff network with NASA and BioSCape Science Team members to both develop long-term relationships and help inform SAEON's use of NASA Earth Data to upscale their in situ observations.
- A Memorandum of Understanding is in the process of being drawn up between NASA and SAEON to support future collaborations, starting with the installation of an [AERONET-OC](#) site in South African waters that will be managed by SAEON. The AERONET-OC site will provide valuable calibration/validation data for PACE and other NASA orbital assets as well as South African researchers.

BioSCape is collaborating closely with both the South African National Parks agency ([SANParks](#)) as well as the provincial protected area agency ([CapeNature](#)) both as members of the Science Team and at upper management and governance levels. These two agencies and their parent departments (the national DFFE and the provincial DEA&DP) are the primary custodians of biodiversity in the BioSCape domain. An outcome of this is that:

- BioSCape has been invited to give four seminars to these agencies (November 2023 and April, May, and June 2024), each to a different level of management (from landscape-level managers to the Chief Executive Officer and Board of CapeNature to the heads of provincial government).

BioSCape gave two seminars to the South African National Department of Water and Sanitation (DWS) about the potential applications of BioSCape and NASA Earth data to water quality assessment (August 2023 and June 2024). Key **outcomes** of these engagements were:

- Increased awareness by high-level decision-making bodies about BioSCape and other NASA Earth Data products.
- At end user's request, BioSCape data will be available locally to preferred data search tools like the [SAEON data portal](#) and easily accessible data visualization tools (e.g. [CapeFarmMapper](#)).

As a result of BioSCape's efforts to collaborate with the South African National Space Agency ([SANSA](#)) (the equivalent of US NASA), the NRF, and the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research ([CSIR](#)), and SAEON several important water quality **outcomes** have occurred:

- A calibration buoy with a spectral radiometer has been installed in Theewaterskloof Dam. The buoy was launched during BioSCape and provided excellent calibration data during the campaign and through to January 2024.
- An AERONET-OC site is being planned for installation near Cape Town later in 2024. The instrument will be an important calibration and validation site for PACE in the southern hemisphere, and will dramatically increase the utility of PACE data for science applications in the BioSCape region.

BioSCape continues to engage with a broad range of government and public academic institutions. An **outcome** of this is that BioSCape has received official letters of support from:

- DFFE: Chief Director: Environmental Knowledge and Information
- DWS: Resource Protection, Scientist Manager
- SANBI: Chief Director, Biodiversity Assessment and Monitoring
- SAEON: Managing Director
- SAEON: Elwandle Node and SMCRI Manager
- CapeNature: Executive Direction of Biodiversity Capabilities
- SANParks: Acting General Manager: Cape Research Centre
- CSIR: Chief Researcher and Head of Precision Agriculture Research Group and Principal Researcher in the Coastal Systems and Earth Observation Research Group
- University of Cape Town: Head of Department, Biological Sciences
- Stellenbosch University: Professor, Geoinformatics
- University of Kwa-Zulu Natal: Professor, Remote Sensing and South African Research Chair
- University of Venda: Senior Lecturer, Department of Geography and Environmental Sciences
- University of Pretoria: Associate Professor, Remote Sensing and Director for the Centre for Environmental Studies
- University of the Western Cape: Professor, Geospatial Sciences
- University of Witwatersrand: Professor, School of Geography, Archaeology, and Environment

Engagement with International Organizations

BioSCape leveraged NASA's commitments to BioSCape to secure funding from the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization ([UNESCO](#)). **Outcomes** of this partnership include:

- Funding to develop capacity and support South African members of the BioSCape Science Team. UNESCO funding is significantly more flexible than US federal funding, especially for expenses such as travel and other activities of non-US-affiliated team

members. Specifically, UNESCO is supporting a South African PhD student and a researcher to attend an international conference, visit a BioSCape PI's lab at a US University for an extended skills exchange, and run a capacity-building workshop.

- The funding is also being used to report to UNESCO on the potential uses of NASA Earth Data to assist in the management of their Biosphere Reserves and World Heritage Sites in the BioSCape study region.

BioSCape is engaged with various NGO's, and most prominently with [The Nature Conservancy](#). The **outcomes** of engagement include:

- The Nature Conservancy is a collaborator on three BioSCape science team projects.
- The Nature Conservancy plans to use BioSCape data to evaluate the effectiveness of its conservation interventions.
- A member of the BioSCape Science Team affiliated with The Nature Conservancy is presenting a tutorial on conducting cloud-native analysis of remote sensing data for biodiversity assessment at The Nature Conservancy's Global Science Gathering. This will be done using an example mapping invasive species in South Africa using EMIT data accessed on AWS.
- BioSCape was invited to present at The Nature Conservancy's Global Spatial Data group's lunchtime webinar.

Engagement with Regional Networks

BioSCape is actively engaged with the activities of the [Fynbos Forum](#) - a regional network of researchers, planners, managers, landowners and a range of other decision makers operating within the Greater Cape Floristic Region. BioSCape has presented at several annual Fynbos Forum meetings since its inception, most recently in September 2022 and August 2023, and will be giving a keynote in August 2024. The **outcomes** of this engagement to date are:

- Increased awareness and involvement of the local research and stakeholder community in the BioSCape Science Team.
- Greater citizen science involvement in data collection via the [iNaturalist](#) platform.
- Increased awareness of how NASA Earth Data can aid in conservation activities, for example the mapping of Invasive Alien Plants.

BioSCape is also engaged with a newer regional action network - the Cape Floristic Region Partnership ([CFRP](#)) - the successor of the [Cape Action for People and the Environment](#) programme, originally funded by the Global Environmental Facility. The CFRP aims to support collaboration, advocacy, learning, and communication among diverse stakeholders with the goal of better conserving the unique biodiversity of the Greater Cape Floristic Region. BioSCape was an invited speaker at the inaugural Knowledge Exchange Event and Annual General Meeting for the CFRP in December 2023 and participated in the CFRP workshop *Bringing research into conservation practice across the Cape Floristic Region* in June 2024. The **outcomes** of these engagements included:

- Increased awareness of the BioSCape data and its potential utility to decision-makers, with particular interest in applications related to the NBA and to mapping Invasive Alien Plants.
- The BioSCape team gained a better understanding of the best ways to collaborate in the future (potential end users and decision-makers indicated that an in-person applications-focused workshop in 2025 would be especially helpful) and to communicate updates to end users (end users indicated they preferred the [BioSCape website](#) and annual written reports).

“There is a big need for another applications workshop. The value creation session was an eye-opening exercise. For an hour and half, researchers listened... it was the beginning of the conversation and it was extremely helpful. It takes NASA coming in to make South Africans talk to each other. We need facilitation of conversations and time to talk.”

– South African decision maker from government agency

BioSCape gave an invited seminar to the Botanical Society of South Africa in June 2024. The society has many members of the public who are interested in biodiversity conservation and citizen science and the society has been instrumental in many biodiversity conservation and outreach initiatives in the region. **Outcomes** of this activity include:

- Increased awareness of BioSCape and NASA's contribution to biodiversity conservation in South Africa.
- Increased goodwill towards the US by South Africans.

Engagement with Landscape Networks

BioSCape gave invited seminars to the Berg River Improvement Project and the Breede Sonderend Catchment Collaborative (June 2023 and August 2024). Both of these landscape networks aim to use scientific data to better manage freshwater supplies around the City of Cape Town. An **outcome** of both engagements was:

- Improved awareness of BioSCape data and a better understanding of how imaging spectroscopy can be used for water quality assessment and improving management of invasive alien plants.

BioSCape participates in the Boland-Groot Winterhoek Strategic Water Source Area Collective's quarterly meetings. The collective aims to coordinate action to address threats/risks/pressures on ecosystems and ecological infrastructure degradation in the region, which is a critical supplier of fresh water to the government of the City of Cape Town. The collective is co-chaired by the provincial DEA&DP and the World Wildlife Fund (WWF; an NGO) and meetings are regularly attended by Local and National Government Institutions as well as various non-governmental organizations (NGOs). An **outcome** of this continued engagement is:

- Increased awareness of the BioSCape data and its potential utility to decision-makers, especially the applications of imaging spectroscopy for water quality and mapping of Invasive Alien Plants that reduce streamflow and increase fire risk.

Contributing to Building and Maintaining the BioSCape Community of Practice

A Community of Practice (COP) is a group of people who "share a concern or a passion for something they do and learn how to do it better as they interact regularly" (Wenger-Trayner & Wenger-Trayner, 2015: p1). **The Impact of BioSCape's COP is an international network of enthusiastic NASA Earth data end users who are gaining the networks and skills to take full advantage of current and future NASA campaigns and missions.** BioSCape's COP includes the Science Team (19 PI-led research projects comprised of ~130 individuals, approximately half of which are from South Africa) as well as other potential end users, including organizations linked to government (national, provincial, and local government and public entities), NGOs (international and South African), research organizations (research organizations and universities), and various regional and landscape level organizations. To build and maintain a COP among these data users, BioSCape created neutral third spaces for

engagement and collaboration and facilitated the co-development of research agendas and plans. These activities and their key outcomes are detailed below.

Earth Science Applications Workshop

BioSCape hosted an in-person workshop in South Africa from 22-26 May 2023 (**Figure 4**). Ninety-four people attended the workshop, representing seven South African Universities, 14 US Universities, and 13 additional end-user groups from local, provincial, and national government, science and research councils, and local and international NGOs. The workshop allowed members of the science team to meet with and listen to the needs of potential end users and take these into account when planning their research. A survey at the workshop identified operational barriers practitioners felt limited their application of Earth Observation data. Overall, potential end users mentioned the lack of information, awareness, and technology (39 instances - 48%) and suggested there were governance, institutional, and/or policy barriers (10 instances - 12%) to using Earth Observation data in their work. This information was useful in the design of capacity-building and outreach activities described below. The workshop also allowed us to showcase South African expertise, with decision-makers from local biodiversity and conservation agencies delivering keynote addresses. This ensured that local ideas, needs, and advice could be incorporated into the research projects' planning.

Key **outcomes** from the Workshop include:

- Educating participants about the technologies to be used, their potential, and the bigger scientific goals of BioSCape in a global context.
- Discussion about the biodiversity research needs of South African decision-makers and the start of mapping pathways for how BioSCape and other NASA Earth Data could meet these needs.
- Creation of networking opportunities and cementing of collaborations between South African and US members of the COP.
- Enhanced goodwill among the South African and US scientific communities, South African government and non-governmental institutions, and NASA.

In a post-campaign survey of the BioSCape science team, multiple people mentioned (unprompted) the importance of the Applications Workshop, indicating that “it was an essential BioSCape activity.” The full [Earth Science Applications Workshop Report provides additional details about the workshop](#).

Figure 4: Photographs from the Earth Science Applications Workshop in 2023, capturing the networking, engagement on applications needs, and social interactions among attendees.

Safeguarding Against Parachute Science

During the development of the BioSCape scoping proposal, the PIs engaged with South African research institutions, including the NRF and SANSA. The **outcomes** of these efforts were:

- The SANSA Chief Scientist was very supportive and explicitly highlighted BioSCape in a funding call in 2021 that resulted in two SA-led projects (total 43 team members) whose research was funded through the NRF’s New Earth Observation Frontiers program, thus ensuring SA scientists were funded to participate in the campaign, though not fully overcoming funding inequities.

BioSCape has worked towards avoiding parachute science from the inception of the project. **Outcomes** of the team’s focus on this include:

- As soon as BioSCape was funded, in the first half of 2021, we hosted an online Networking Workshop. This introductory workshop covered developments within the initial phases of BioSCape. It included presentations by the BioSCape PIs, NASA, the University of Cape Town, SANBI, SAEON, SANParks, and CapeNature.
- BioSCape ran a workshop (co-hosted by SANBI and the University of California Santa Cruz) that introduced the “Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilization to the Convention on Biological Diversity” and explained how to comply with it. The workshop included putting together a document outlining the shared benefits of each team’s planned research, detailing the ways both South African and US counterparts benefitted from the research. Such a document was important for managing expectations and keeping teams focused on the benefits of international collaboration.
- The team also ran a 2021 American Geophysical Union Fall Meeting workshop entitled *Meaningful and Equitable Collaboration: How to Avoid Parachute Science*.

- In 2022, BioSCape organized an online Parachute Science Workshop. This workshop overviewed challenges and outlined pivotal steps in preventing parachute science with a focus on projects related to remote sensing of the environment and biodiversity.
- Over 100 BioSCape Science Team members underwent “Ethical Participation” pre-field training (September 2023). The training covered the BioSCape Code of Conduct, methods for conflict resolution in the field, basic field safety in South Africa, and the country's historical, sociopolitical, and cultural context.
- Inclusive authorship guidelines are included in the BioSCape [Code of Conduct](#), which all team members are obliged to comply with.

Public Engagement Event

BioSCape, in partnership with the University of Cape Town and with funding from UNESCO, organized a public lecture event on 17 November 2023 (**Figure 5**). The event was attended by ~150 people, which included 25 people from provincial and local government organizations, 16 people from national government organizations, 75 people from universities and research institutions (many not directly involved in BioSCape), 16 people from private organizations (e.g. environmental consultancies), 12 people from NGOs, and members of the public. Key **outcomes** from the Public Engagement Event include:

- Increased awareness and support for BioSCape across a broad range of stakeholders.
- Platforming of South African expertise in the form of keynote addresses from decision-makers at SAEON, SANBI, CSIR, and the University of Cape Town.

Figure 5: Photographs of speakers and audience at the BioSCape Public Lecture that took place at University of Cape Town, South Africa.

Increased Collaboration for Broader Impact

BioSCape continues to engage in regular meetings, workshops, and events with key end users. As a result of these engagements, BioSCape facilitated several notable collaborations. Key **outcomes** of these facilitation activities are:

- Three people at SANBI connected with a BioSCape Science Team member and wrote a successful [DEVELOP](#) proposal that is being implemented June-August 2024 at the Jet Propulsion Lab. This project will investigate the utility of NASA Earth Data for mapping riparian vegetation, a critical component of the NBA.
- A member of the BioSCape Science Team submitted a successful proposal funded through NASA's Earth Surface and Interior Program. The successful proposal was for the expansion of BioSCape work to include more South African collaborators and produce additional data products requested by end users at SANBI, including maps of surface mineralogy in the region.
- The national DWS is collaborating with the CSIR, a public entity research organization, to build capacity in Earth Observation data skills that can be used for water quality monitoring. This collaboration has also led to the national DWS now being represented in the Technical Advisory Group for the National Oceans and Coastal Information Management System ([OCIMS](#), Water Quality tool). In the future, this collaboration aims to expand OCIMS's scope to include estuarine and freshwater decision support.

Capacity Building and Open Science to Increase Future Benefit of NASA Earth Data

BioSCape endeavors to follow FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles. To do this, data not only has to be Open Access, but it also needs to be accessible. A large barrier to data accessibility in South Africa is technical capacity and access to computing resources. To help address this, BioSCape, in collaboration with NASA's Science Managed Cloud Environment and Amazon Web Services, has set up a cloud computing environment and is running several capacity-building workshops for end users, summarized below. **The impact of these activities is that South African end-users understand NASA Earth Data and how to use it, which increases their perceived value of these data and makes it more likely they will continue to use these and forthcoming NASA Earth Data to make decisions.**

Capacity Building

BioSCape partnered with NASA's Applied Remote Sensing Training Program ([ARSET](#)) to deliver a [4-part webinar series](#) (April 2023). The training was attended by 1,342 participants from 108 countries and nearly 900 organizations, of which 38 were South African. The **outcomes** of this training are that participants can now:

- Understand the applications of hyperspectral data, multispectral data, and LiDAR data for biodiversity monitoring and analysis.
- Utilize existing datasets in preparation for upcoming NASA satellite missions and airborne campaigns.

BioSCape partnered with the University of Wisconsin Madison, University of California Merced, and the University of Cape Town to deliver a 2-day in-person field spectroscopy training workshop for local researchers and end users (October 2023) (**Figure 6**). The **outcomes** of this training are that participants now understand:

- What spectroscopy is and what it can tell us about plants and water bodies.
- How a field spectrometer works, how to use it to collect data, and how to process the data.

BioSCape Science Team members delivered a 2-day in-person Autonomous Audio Survey training at the University of Cape Town (November 2023). An **outcome** of the training was:

- The training of a team of citizen scientists and NGO staff in methods relating to “Soundscapes” including *Arbimon*, a cloud-based audio analysis system.

BioSCape Science Team members, in partnership with the CSIR, the national DWS, and an NGO (Digital Earth Africa) ran a 2-day in-person training about Water Monitoring Applications for Remote Sensing (June 2024). The training course was funded by the Marine and Coastal Operations for southern Africa and the Indian Ocean ([MarCOSIO](#)) project under the [GMES & Africa](#) programme. The **outcomes** of this training included:

- Increased awareness of BioSCape and other NASA Earth data for aquatic applications.
- Participants gained the skills to extract basic water quality metrics from satellite data products in a cloud computing environment.

BioSCape partnered with [COMPASS Science Communication](#) to deliver a 4-day science communication workshop to 20 members of the BioSCape Science Team - 7 from South Africa and 13 from the US with 50% participation by Early Career Researchers (September 2023). The key **outcome** of this activity was:

- Improved science communication abilities by the Science Team, especially Early Career Researchers.

BioSCape partnered with NASA’s Oak Ridge National Laboratory’s Distributed Data Archive Center ([ORNL DAAC](#)) to deliver a pre-campaign workshop about data best practices (September 2023). The **outcomes** of this workshop were:

- An increased understanding of NASA’s Open Science strategy by the BioSCape Science Team.
- The creation of a persistent resource that introduces the best practices for data collection, and specifically creation of metadata, as well as clear instructions on how and when to archive your data.

Figure 6: Photographs of participants and speakers at the field spectroscopy training at the University of Cape Town and at the water monitoring training at the CSIR.

In October 2024, BioSCape will host a 5-day in-person field spectroscopy and data analysis workshop in Cape Town, South Africa. The workshop is being delivered by NASA's ARSET and ORNL DAAC with significant support from SAEON, the University of Cape Town, the University of Wisconsin Madison, the University of California Merced, the Jet Propulsion Laboratory, and NASA's Science Managed Cloud Environment. This workshop will focus on linking field, airborne, and orbital measurements from BioSCape. An anticipated workshop **outcome** includes:

- Preparing the user community to continue their use of NASA Earth Data, specifically EMIT, ECOSTRESS, GEDI, PACE, and SBG.

Education and Outreach

BioSCape has supported several education and outreach activities. These activities and their outcomes are detailed below.

BioSCape also supported NASA's Global Learning and Observations to benefit the Environment Program ([GLOBE](#)) in building collaborations with SAEON, the [South African Agency for Science and Technology Advancement](#), and the [Cape Winelands Biosphere Reserve](#) to run science programs for 170 high-school students from 10 under-resourced schools (November & December 2023), and for educators that participated in the GLOBE "train the trainer" program (November 2023) (**Figure 7**).

BioSCape collaborated with various schools, government organizations, and NGOs to host three SpaceApps Hackathon events around the greater Cape Town area (October 2023). The BioSCape Science Team supported SAEON in their annual Graduate Student Network conference ("Indibano") by having various members of BioSCape give talks and workshops and judge student presentations (October 2023) (**Figure 8**).

The **outcomes** of all the above activities were:

- Pre-university capacity building in the fields of science and technology, specifically Earth Observation.
- Increased goodwill between the United States and South Africa.
- Increased positive regard for NASA internationally.

Figure 7: Photographs of NASA GLOBE school learners and trainers and NASA Space Apps participants.

Figure 8: Photographs of participants and speakers at the SAEON Graduate Student Network conference.

Science Communication to Promote Positive Perception of NASA Earth Data

In the lead up to the BioSCape field campaign, diplomatic relationships were particularly strained between the United States and South Africa due to ongoing geopolitical issues. There has also historically been skepticism about the United States's good intentions when conducting activities in South Africa. Consequently, BioSCape was intentional and careful in its approach to communicating with the public about the campaign. The **impact of our mindful approach was that media features about the campaign were all positive, leading to a positive perception of NASA Earth Observation by the public.** This was achieved through several key activities:

- A comprehensive and regularly updated project website: www.bioscape.io
 - Our website includes details on the origin of BioSCape, project sponsorship and institutional support, as well as a review of the science and research taking place.
- Early communication of the campaign and its goals to the public as soon as BioSCape was selected in 2021, as well as many media features prior to and during the airborne campaign component.
 - All press features are available on our project website press page: www.bioscape.io/news
- Creation of a communications strategy in collaboration with the Western Cape Government, the United States State Department, NASA Communications Office, SAEON, the South African National Space Agency ([SANSA](#)), to help coordinate communication during the campaign.
 - This resulted in multiple flattering media features ([available here](#)), including a feature from a South African news outlet that “debunked” a conspiracy theory about the “nefarious NASA planes” that had been circulating on social media.
 - The communications strategy was shared with key project partners so that they were equipped to answer any questions that might arise about the campaign.
- Various science communications materials were produced by two NASA Science Communications interns.
 - This included a written “BioSCape Origins, Meaning, and Legacy” story, a [storymap and interactive project timeline](#), an interactive [BioSCape Science Team organogram](#), and various visual materials shared on BioSCape’s social media accounts ([X](#) and [Instagram](#)).

Understanding Potential End User Needs for NASA Earth Data

Being a once-off, geographically isolated field campaign, BioSCape has limited potential to produce data products suitable for long-term continued use. However, BioSCape data does have the potential to be used in decision-making and benefit several South African end users, as is detailed in the proceeding sections. The **impact of this is increasing the understanding and likelihood of sustained use of NASA Earth Data by South Africa end users, particularly PACE, EMIT, ECOSTRESS, and GEDI, and preparing end users to be NISAR and SBG early adopters.**

NASA Earth Data for the National Biodiversity Assessment (NBA) and Associated National Biodiversity Data Products

End User Decision Making Need

Like many regions worldwide, South Africa needs to support human development while conserving its biodiversity in the face of climate change. The broader BioSCape study region has the second highest documented number of vascular plant extinctions in the world, over half of marine and coastal ecosystems are threatened, and nearly half of marine fisheries are over-exploited or collapsed. A key part of measuring, monitoring, and protecting biodiversity is producing accurate reports on the state of biodiversity so that appropriate management decisions can be made. South Africa's primary mechanism for doing this at a national scale is the NBA. The NBA is the official national evaluation of South African biodiversity and is the mandate of SANBI. It reports on the status of species, ecosystems and genetic diversity and their contributions to the wellbeing of South Africans across marine, terrestrial and inland water realms. The NBA directly influences policy and strategy in the biodiversity sector, helps prioritize biodiversity conservation and management resources, is a key component of academic research in the region, and underpins South Africa's reporting on its progress towards The Biodiversity Plan's Goals and Targets.

The NBA has a direct impact on biodiversity conservation in South Africa. Key informants of and headline indicators used in the NBA include national-level assessments of threats to species and ecosystems in South Africa, which are coordinated by SANBI. While these assessments typically form part of the NBA, they also stand alone as independent products in that SANBI is mandated to produce them by law, and the national lists of [species](#) and [ecosystems](#) that are threatened or in need of protection are written into law by the National Minister of Environmental Affairs. The legal status of these lists prioritizes these species and ecosystems for conservation and puts limits on development and land use practices within their habitats ([National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Act 10 of 2004](#)). While the first national species and ecosystem threat assessments predate the IUCN Red List of Ecosystems and Red List of Threatened Species, they have been central in informing the IUCN approaches and have now adopted the IUCN criteria and protocols.

While the threat assessments synthesize a range of data from *in situ* observations to expert opinion, NASA Earth Data have and will continue to inform them through the mapping of ecosystem and habitat extents and perceived threats. For example, the core of the ecosystem threat assessments are based on maps of the historical extent of ecosystems combined with land cover products to quantify the extent and rate of ecosystem loss. Currently, the National Ecosystem Maps of ecosystem extent use a combination of field and remote sensing data. Data sources vary depending on the type of ecosystem, but can include expert opinion, field data, geological maps, citizen scientist observations of species presence/absence, aerial RGB imagery, and multispectral satellite data products (most frequently from Landsat and Sentinel-2). Most NBA outputs are at 30 m spatial resolution. Unfortunately, these assessments are currently based on the categorical loss of ecosystem extent (based on land cover maps indicating conversion to a non-natural land cover type) and do not consider degrading processes that reduce ecological conditions such as the presence of invasive species, altered fire or herbivory regimes, or climate change. This is due to the challenges with evaluating these threats when spectral and temporal resolution of data are limited. These are issues that BioSCape can help address, and that hopefully other NASA Earth Data can continue to address in the future.

While most threatened ecosystems and species in South Africa fall within the BioSCape domain, there is great desire to implement high-fidelity and scalable approaches to measure ecosystem condition across all ecosystem types in South Africa. This could even be scaled to other countries in the southern African region as SANBI is the lead implementing agent in an intergovernmental [project to map ecological condition and assess threats to ecosystems](#) in South Africa, Namibia, Mozambique and Malawi. South African BioSCape PI, Slingsby, is a collaborator on the project and presented on BioSCape and NASA Earth Data at the [inaugural workshop](#) for the project in November 2023.

BioSCape and NASA Earth Data have potential to impact the NBA through knowledge gain, specifically by leveraging imaging spectroscopy, thermal infrared, and LiDAR data-driven approaches i) to improve ecosystem extent mapping in some regions for some ecosystems and ii) to improve assessment of ecological condition and threats to species and ecosystems. SANBI is responsible for facilitating contributions to ultimately producing the NBA, but the NBA is produced by synthesizing information from many subject-matter experts across academic, research, government, and NGO institutions and SANBI itself. The report writing is coordinated by SANBI, with several experts volunteering to lead the writing and research in each technical report (one technical report for each set of ecosystem realms and key thematic areas). BioSCape is in regular communication with the lead of NBA at SANBI, who is enthusiastic about the potential of BioSCape and other NASA Earth Data to improve the NBA, and who attended BioSCape's 2023 Earth Science Applications workshop and public outreach event.

“Some landscape changes may be subtle and require in-situ data for accurate understanding...and higher resolution hyperspectral remote sensing data (like BioSCape) can be used to monitor plant community shifts and map layers of disturbance to vegetation units, providing practitioners with a more comprehensive view of biodiversity changes.”
– South African decision maker from public entity

Potential Data Sources

BioSCape will provide an excellent proof of concept for potential future sustained approaches that use NASA Earth Data products. Certain BioSCape data products may inform the NBA, but the biggest impact of NASA Earth Data on the NBA will be gained from scaling up the approaches tested in BioSCape to use data from NASA's [Earth Observing System](#).

Several BioSCape data products will be particularly useful to meet end-user needs (data provider in brackets):

- High-resolution Digital Elevation Models and vegetation height products (LVIS).
- Evapotranspiration data products derived from HyTES and ECOSTRESS (Cawse-Nicholson).
- Maps of alpha, beta, and gamma spectral diversity derived from AVIRIS-NG (Cawse-Nicholson).
- Map of plant communities based on principal components analysis done in certain regions using AVIRIS-NG data (Brodrick).
- Plant functional trait maps derived from AVIRIS-NG (Townsend).
- Kelp fractional cover and physiological condition maps derived from AVIRIS-NG (Bell).
- Maps of estuarine vegetation types and quantifying several Essential Biodiversity Variables in important estuaries distributed along the South African coastline derived from AVIRIS-NG (Stovall).

- Imaging spectroscopy algorithms for mapping common alien invasive plant species using AVIRIS-NG data (Adler).
- Vegetation plot data (Townsend, Slingsby, Fitzpatrick, Cho, Meyer).
- Maps of common invasive alien plants in certain study regions derived from AVIRIS-NG (Adler).
- Point counts and audio-derived estimates of diversity in birds and frogs, and description of remote sensing-derived bird and frog biodiversity predictors (Clark).
- DNA Sequence data (Fitzpatrick).
- eDNA-derived biodiversity metrics (Meyer).
- Mineral maps derived from EMIT, HyTES, and AVIRIS-NG (Cawse-Nicholson).

Outside of the scope of currently funded BioSCape activities, there are several data sources or activities that would be useful for promoting sustained use of NASA Earth data in the NBA:

- Algorithms and maps to delineate the extent and severity of invasion by numerous alien plant species derived from EMIT data and informed by contemporaneous AVIRIS-NG and EMIT acquisitions.
- Algorithms and maps of coastal vegetation type (including kelp and estuaries) and ecological condition derived from EMIT and PACE and informed by contemporaneous AVIRIS-NG, PRISM, and EMIT acquisitions.
- Development of data pipelines to map and monitor ecological condition using EMIT, informed by contemporaneous AVIRIS-NG and EMIT acquisitions.
- Mapping of riparian and ephemeral wetland ecosystems across the region using AVIRIS-NG, LVIS, EMIT, and GEDI acquisitions, with the intention of using NISAR in the future.

Barriers to Sustainable Use by the End User

Since derived BioSCape data products will only be available in early 2025, they have not yet been shared with SANBI and other authors of the NBA. When these products are shared, we anticipate capacity building to be necessary for the data products to have maximum impact. Since BioSCape Science Team members are not currently funded through 2025, we anticipate only select people will have the capacity to deeply engage with South African users and share their specific expertise. Therefore, the necessary capacity building could take place at a future Earth Science Applications workshop, and continue through technical support for the BioSCape cloud, which would help end users with data analysis questions, with more specific issues addressed through meetings with available science team members, facilitated by BioSCape.

NASA Earth Data for Water Quality Measurement and Monitoring

End User Decision-Making Need

The coastline and freshwater reservoirs of South Africa suffer from Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs). HABs have significant economic effects on South Africa through their impacts on biodiversity, aquaculture, fishing industries (commercial and subsistence), and tourism. HABs are expected to become more extensive and frequent in the future, and early prediction and early warning systems are a crucial part of mitigating their negative impacts. South Africa monitors and manages coastal ecosystems using the National Oceans and Coastal Information Management System ([OCIMS](#)). OCIMS includes several operational decision-support tools, including a [Water Quality tool](#) and a [Fisheries and Aquaculture tool](#). OCIMS directly influences decisions in the aquaculture and commercial and subsistence fishing industries, who change activity patterns based on HAB early warnings. It also influences decisions in disaster

management sectors of government, such as when and where to close beaches, which has an impact on local economies.

Currently, OCIMS uses Sentinel-2 data products at 10 m and 60 m spatial resolution (every five days) as well as Sentinel-3 data products at 300 m (ocean color) and 1 km (thermal) spatial resolution (every day). While these data products provide relatively good information to decision-makers, they could be substantially improved by increasing their spectral and temporal resolution. Improvements to OCIMS would help better detect and monitor the movement of HABs as well as the concentration and type of other phytoplankton. It would also enable better detection of pollutants, such as sewage effluent, and to monitor the safety of areas with high levels of river discharge. OCIMS is not yet used for inland water quality monitoring, but there is interest in an inland waters tool that can be used to inform decisions around drinking water quality and quantity, and pilot tools are in development (e.g. Earth Observation for Water Quality, [EO4WQ](#)).

BioSCape and NASA Earth Data have the potential to impact water quality measurement through knowledge gain, specifically by leveraging imaging spectroscopy approaches to measure water quality and detect HABs. OCIMS is run by the national DFFE in partnership with the CSIR, SAEON, and the South African Weather Service. The BioSCape Science Team includes key OCIMS developers and users from the national DFFE, the CSIR, and SAEON, all of whom are enthusiastic about including imaging spectroscopy into the OCIMS data pipeline.

“For the first time in our records, unprecedented levels of harmful cyanobacteria have been reported in the Berg River, which has implications for the protection of wildlife, livestock, and human populations.”
– South African decision-makers from national government

Potential Data Sources

BioSCape will provide an excellent proof of concept for potential future sustained approaches that use NASA Earth Data products. Specifically, BioSCape data products may inform the development of algorithms for water quality monitoring and HAB detection. However, the biggest impacts of NASA Earth Data on OCIMS will be gained from scaling up the approaches trialed in BioSCape to use data from NASA’s [Earth Observing System](#), and specifically from PACE (1 km spatial resolution, 1-2 day revisit) and EMIT (60 m spatial resolution, ~2 week revisit). Both PACE and EMIT could be useful for coastal marine, estuarine, and freshwater bodies (including wetlands and rivers).

Several BioSCape data products will be particularly useful to meet end-user needs (data provider in brackets):

- Calibration data from the spectral radiometer in Theewaterskloof Dam (Van Niekerk).
- Phytoplankton microscopy (Wu, Guild, Van Niekerk).
- FlowCAM derived phytoplankton species data (Wu, Guild, Van Niekerk).
- HPLC pigments (Wu, Guild, Van Niekerk).
- Algorithms for mapping phytoplankton functional types from PRISM data (Wu, Guild, Van Niekerk).
- Marine inorganic nutrient data (Wu, Guild, Van Niekerk).
- 3-D fluorescence signatures of coloured dissolved organic matter (CDOM) (Tzortziou).
- CDOM absorption spectra and slope estimates (Tzortziou).

Outside of the scope of currently funded BioSCape activities, there are several data sources or activities that would be useful for promoting sustained use of NASA Earth data for water quality measurement and monitoring in South Africa:

- Scaling up algorithms for phytoplankton measurement using PRISM to be applicable to data from PACE and implementing this new workflow within the existing OCIMS tools.

Barriers to Sustainable Use by the End User

PACE's spatial resolution being 1 km is suboptimal for OCIMS applications, however there is potential to pair acquisitions with EMIT's 60 m spatial resolution to improve monitoring outcomes. Developing PACE and EMIT specific algorithms from the expected AVIRIS-NG algorithms will take additional researcher funding and commitment from the science team, as will implementation of these methods into the OCIMS data processing pipeline.

NASA Earth Data for Management of Invasive Alien Plants

End User Decision Making Need (1)

Invasive alien plants are not only a threat to biodiversity but are also a threat to fresh water supply. Alien invasive trees displace native plants and have greater biomass and deeper roots, increasing rainfall interception and evapotranspiration and depleting deeper soil water layers. This reduces runoff and recharge of dams and groundwater. They also increase erosion and sedimentation in dams by increasing the available fuel load for wildfires. Consequently, controlling the threat of alien invasive plants is one of the four investment priorities identified by the provincial Western Cape Government in their [Ecological Infrastructure Investment Framework](#). The framework specifically identifies a lack of capacity to identify the early stages of invasion as a key constraint to achieving their objectives, as early detection facilitates rapid, cost-saving interventions.

In addition to the NBA and related work, SANBI is also mandated to report on [The Status of Biological Invasions and their Management in South Africa](#) every three years. While there have been attempts to map invasive species with remote sensing in the region, the results to date do not meet the monitoring and management requirements. The two most recent status reports highlight this unrealized potential, e.g. *“Remote sensing is still a promising approach to improve distribution data, but has not yet delivered tangible results that can be used in this report. There continue to be very few reliable data sources on the relative abundance (cover, biomass or population size) of alien species at specific sites. National and local scale estimates and maps of the impact of invasions are needed to appropriately prioritise interventions across sites and so that interventions can be adjusted to respond to invasions before such invasions are widespread and damaging.”*

There have been two National Invasive Alien Plant Surveys (NIAPS), generated by a government contractor in 2010 (maps dates 2008) and 2024 (map dates unknown, but likely spanning 2013-2017). The contractor executing NIAPS does not openly distribute all of the source data and exact methods for producing the extent map are not clearly articulated in the publicly available report. It is thought that the 2010 maps are created using a modeling approach based on a combination of MODIS, aerial imagery, and field data, creating a product with 250 m spatial resolution. NIAPS was last published in 2024 and included South Africa's National Aerial Imagery to generate a product at 50 cm spatial resolution. Unfortunately, uncertainty about methods and the dates of data used for the mapping limit its utility for invasive species management or repeatability. Another research project run by [Agricultural Research](#)

[Council](#) (Mapping Woody invasive Alien Plant Species - [MapWAPs](#)) is using Sentinel-2 and an Open Science approach to map invasions in a selection of [Strategic Water Source Areas](#) and across the Western Cape province. They hope to scale this approach to the whole country in the future, and their Open Science approach would make their analyses repeatable and maps updatable. CapeNature and SANParks conduct ground and aerial surveys and produce annual maps of the extent of alien invasive plants in key parts of their protected areas, but capacity for extensive field surveys is limited. The [Greater Cape Town Water Fund](#), a multi-sectoral partnership facilitated by The Nature Conservancy, works with the City of Cape Town municipality, the South African National Department of Environmental Affairs' [Working for Water](#) program, and other partners to clear alien invasive plants and improve freshwater supply. The Nature Conservancy is particularly interested in remote sensing approaches to (a) improve early detection of invasions, and (b) improve estimates of water losses to invasive species.

BioSCape and NASA Earth Data have potential to impact water supply by improving mapping of invasive alien plant extent and severity and their impacts through knowledge gain, specifically by leveraging imaging spectroscopy approaches to i) more accurately delineate different alien species from another, ii) more accurately detect early or low-density invasions, and iii) improve estimates of key parameters used to drive hydrological models of the impacts of invasions on water supply. BioSCape's Science Team contains key personnel from the Agricultural Research Council and the MapWAPs project, the Nature Conservancy and the Greater Cape Town Water Fund, SANBI, CapeNature, and SANParks. BioSCape has also built a close partnership with the provincial Western Cape Government. As such, data products and approaches generated within BioSCape have a high likelihood of impact within these organizations.

"IAPs mapping for agriculture, specifically the monitoring and management of eucalyptus and pine plantations, has been greatly aided by the use of Landsat and Sentinel data in the past. Furthermore, the integration of remote sensing data has proven crucial in the development of fire management plans, allowing for more informed decision making in this area."

– South African decision maker from public entity

Potential Data Sources (1)

Several BioSCape data products will be particularly useful to meet end-user needs (data provider in brackets):

- Algorithms that map several important invasive alien trees from AVIRIS-NG acquisitions (Adler).
- Maps of invasion extent and severity in certain study regions derived from AVIRIS-NG and LVIS data (Adler).

Outside of the scope of currently funded BioSCape activities, there are several data sources or activities that would be useful for promoting sustained use of NASA Earth Data for mapping the extent and severity of alien invasions:

- Maps of invasion extent and severity for several important invasive alien plant species across the full BioSCape study region using AVIRIS-NG acquisitions.
- Field data and maps of invasion extent and severity for several additional invasive alien plant species across the full BioSCape study region using AVIRIS-NG acquisitions.
- Scaling up algorithms for invasion extent and severity using AVIRIS-NG to be applicable to data from EMIT and implementing this new workflow within the existing Greater Cape Town Water fund pipeline.

- Improving hydrological models with better estimates of vegetation structure (LVIS) and evapotranspiration rates from natural versus invasive vegetation (HyTES).

Barriers to Sustainable Use by the End User (1)

High-fidelity maps of a range of invasive alien species require additional field data. While BioSCape was funded to collect some of this field data, data on additional species is required. Additionally, funding for key researchers at the Nature Conservancy to scale up algorithms and methods used in BioSCape to cover a larger area and to use data from NASA's Earth Observing System is required to increase the likelihood of sustained use within the Greater Cape Town Water Fund.

End User Decision Making Need (2)

The removal of invasive alien plants is the greatest restoration priority in the BioSCape study region. A key need in this regard is tools to monitor the effectiveness of restoration in terms of the recovery of the structure, composition, and function of biodiversity. This is needed by CapeNature, SANParks, the provincial DEA&DP, the national DFFE, SANBI, the Nature Conservancy, and other organizations for a range of reasons, including so that they can compare and improve restoration methods; to quantify the benefits of restoration for biodiversity and nature's contributions to people so as to make the case to the public, funders and government decision-makers that restoration efforts are worthwhile; and to assess ecological condition to inform species and ecosystem threat assessments.

Existing approaches predominantly depend on expensive and logistically constrained field surveys. In another NASA-funded Earth Science Applications [project](#) parallel to BioSCape, PI Wilson and South African Lead Slingsby have developed an approach based on Normalised Difference Vegetation Index time-series that can assess whether restored areas have returned to something resembling their natural function in terms of productivity and seasonality, but this approach currently cannot directly assess structure or composition.

BioSCape and NASA Earth Data have potential to impact the restoration of native ecosystems by improving reporting on changes to ecological condition as a result of alien species removal. Many BioSCape science team members are already embedded in decision-making organizations in this area, and have repeatedly expressed interest in this contribution from the project.

Potential Data Sources (2)

Several BioSCape data products will be particularly useful to meet end-user needs (data provider in brackets):

- Radiative transfer model-derived synthetic spectral data that can be used to predict the spectral and structural signals that the BioSCape sensors should see in impacted versus intact vegetation of different post-fire vegetation ages. These products can, in the future, be used as counterfactuals for early detection of anomalies (including invasion) in native vegetation after fire or restoration activities (Van Aardt).
- Maps of the spectral dimensionality of more and less invaded ecosystems in certain regions (Cawse-Nicholson).
- Maps of essential biodiversity variables in more and less invaded ecosystems in certain regions (Fitzpatrick).
- Data on the impact of invasive alien plants on water use efficiency, a key component of measuring the impact of restoration on nature's contribution to people (Adler).

- Data on the impact of invasive alien plants on fuel load for fire, a key component of measuring the negative impact of invasion on nature's contribution to people (Adler).
- Maps of plant functional traits across invaded and uninvaded landscapes (Townsend).

Outside of the scope of currently funded BioSCape activities, there are several data sources or activities that would be useful for promoting sustained use of NASA Earth Data for assessing ecological condition as a result of alien invasion and subsequent restoration:

- Development of imaging spectroscopy-based methods, specifically using EMIT, to monitor recovery after alien clearing and implementation of these within the existing Greater Cape Town Water fund decision making processes.
- Creating data pipelines that can incorporate synthetic spectral datasets into decision making for alien invasive management.
- Quantitative analysis of how alien invasions impact the water supply of the BioSCape study region using remote-sensing derived evapotranspiration.
- Developing approaches to scale algorithms used to assess ecosystem function using AVIRIS-NG data to be applicable to data from EMIT.
- Investigating the effect of invasion on fire regimes - both from a biomass (LVIS) and a flammable compound (AVIRIS-NG) perspective.

Barriers to Sustainable Use by the End User (2)

The barriers to implementing BioSCape and NASA Earth Data into assessing ecological condition as a result of invasion and restoration all center around the novel nature of the research and the outstanding steps needed to make research data products usable for decision-makers. The potential benefit in this area is clear, but sustained efforts to communicate BioSCape data products to end users, execute capacity-building events, and continue communication between US BioSCape Science Team members and South African decision-makers, many of whom are also on the BioSCape Science Team, will require sustained effort over time. Some of the necessary capacity building could take place at a future Science Applications workshop, and continue through technical support for the BioSCape cloud, which would help end users with data analysis questions, with more specific issues addressed through meetings with available BioSCape Science Team members, facilitated by BioSCape Leadership. Importantly - a barrier that is *not* present is a lack of enthusiasm around this area of research from South African end users and decision-makers, all of whom are excited and enthusiastic about the potential of BioSCape and NASA Earth Data for this application.

Looking Forward

There is abundant interest from the South African end-user decision-making community about BioSCape and NASA Earth Data for the above applications. Over the coming year, BioSCape will continue to develop and document the impact of this airborne campaign in South Africa and globally. We will also continue to document the realized and potential impact of other NASA Earth Data and the way that BioSCape data products supported this impact. The expected **outcomes** of these activities include:

- Ensuring that BioSCape data products are made available in a timely manner to South African end users, especially those who may use the data to make decisions.
- Delivering a capacity-building workshop in Cape Town, South Africa. The workshop will train potential end users and decision-makers in how to use field spectrometers and how to open, view, and analyze both BioSCape data products and other relevant NASA Earth data sets.

- This training is a collaboration between BioSCape and NASA's ARSET and Oak Ridge National Laboratory Distributed Active Archive Center (ORNL DAAC) as well as SAEON, the University of Wisconsin, Madison, The Nature Conservancy, the University of California Merced, the University of Cape Town, the Jet Propulsion Laboratory, and UNESCO.
- Continued facilitated discussion between potential end users and decision-makers in South Africa and relevant members of the BioSCape Science Team, with a focus on supporting the end users and potential Earth Science Applications detailed in this report.
- Continued participation in regional networks and conferences to ensure BioSCape results and products are used to their full potential.
- Follow-ups with the specific potential end users identified in this report and document the extent to which BioSCape and other NASA Earth Data is being used in decision-making.

Additionally, we are actively looking for additional funding to support a second Earth Science Applications Workshop in 2025. At the workshop, we would host South African end users and decision-makers and key members of the BioSCape Science Team who are producing data products with specific relevance to South African Earth Science Applications. We would also invite the Applications Leads from SBG, EMIT, PACE, ECOSTRESS, and GEDI since much of the potential impact of BioSCape will be felt through onboarding of South African end-users onto more continuous NASA Earth Data imaging spectroscopy and LiDAR data products. There is also potential to include the Applications Lead from NiSAR, as the South African community is likely to have interest in this upcoming mission. The **outcomes** of this workshop would include:

- Increase the likelihood that BioSCape data products are used to inform decision-making in South Africa.
 - This would close the loop on the most promising BioSCape Earth Science Applications as identified at the previous Earth Science Applications workshop and throughout the campaign and establish how these products need to be tailored to feed into existing decision-making frameworks. We believe this is necessary because while stakeholders have expressed interest and excitement, there are many steps between a research data product and one that applies to decision-making.
- Scoping of how the needs of a decision maker(s) can best be met by SBG and its precursor missions (specifically EMIT, PACE, and ECOSTRESS).
 - This would be done by showcasing the potential value of NASA Earth Data, especially imaging spectroscopy, by demonstrating the logical application of the approaches in BioSCape to SBG and its precursor data products.
 - Structured discussions with end users would also help us better scope SBG data needs from end users. This is especially important to do in countries outside of the US to ensure that SBG data are more widely applicable.
- Creating opportunities for the formation of an SBG early adopter community by South African end users, as well as feeding users into the PACE and EMIT early adopter communities.

Given BioSCape's geographic focus, all of these activities are necessarily centered on a single country, but as South Africa is a global leader in biodiversity policy and management, we feel that innovations developed here have great potential to be adopted by others and scaled to have global impact.

Glossary

AERONET-OC	Aerosol Robotic Network - Ocean Color.
ARSET	NASA's Applied Remote Sensing and Training Program.
AVIRIS-NG	Airborne Visible/Infrared Imaging Spectrometer, Next Generation. An imaging spectrometer flown in BioSCape.
CapeNature	Provincial conservation entity.
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity.
CFRP	Cape Floristic Region Partnership.
COP	Community of Practise.
CSIR	Council for Scientific and Industrial Research.
DEA&DP	The Western Cape Provincial Department of Environmental Affairs and Development Planning.
DEVELOP	A NASA capacity building program.
DFFE	South Africa's National Department of Forestry, Fisheries, and Environment.
DWS	South Africa's National Department of Water and Sanitation.
ECOSTRESS	ECOsystem Spaceborne Thermal Radiometer Experiment on Space Station. NASA's thermal radiometer on the International Space Station.
EMIT	Earth Surface Mineral Dust Source Investigation. NASA's imaging spectrometer on the International Space Station.
GEDI	Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation. NASA's LiDAR instrument on the International Space Station.
GLOBE	NASA's Global Learning and Observations to benefit the Environment Program.
HyTES	Hyperspectral Thermal Emissions Spectrometer. A thermal radiometer flown in BioSCape.
IUCN	International Union for the Conservation of Nature.
Landsat	A set of multispectral satellites run by NASA and the United States Geological Survey.
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging.
LTER	Long-Term Ecological Research Network related to NEON.
LVIS	Land, Vegetation, and Ice Sensor. A full waveform LiDAR instrument flown in BioSCape.
MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer. A set of multispectral satellites run by NASA.
NASA	The United States National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NBA	National Biodiversity Assessment of South Africa
NEMBA	South African National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Act.
NEON	The US's National Ecological Observatory Network.
NIAPS	The South African National Invasive Alien Plant Surveys.
NISAR	NASA-ISRO Synthetic Aperture Radar. An upcoming radar satellite.
NRF	South African National Research Foundation.
OCIMS	National Oceans and Coastal Information Management System
ORNL DAAC	NASA's Oak Ridge National Laboratory Distributed Active Archiving Center.
PACE	Plankton, Aerosol, Cloud, ocean Ecosystem. An imaging spectrometer satellite.
PI	Principal Investigator.
PRISM	Portable Remote Imaging SpectroMeter. An imaging spectrometer flown in BioSCape.
SAEON	The South African Environmental Observation Network.
SANBI	South African National Biodiversity Institute.
SANSA	South African National Space Agency.
SBG	Surface Biology and Geology. An upcoming thermal radiometry and imaging spectroscopy satellite mission.
Sentinel	A set of multispectral satellites run by the European Space Agency.
SOBR	State of Biodiversity Report.
The Biodiversity Plan	The Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework.
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.
WCG	The Western Cape Provincial Government.
WWF	World Wildlife Fund.

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